

Autonomous Vehicle Positioning with LiDAR-only Sensing: an Application on the RACECAR Dataset

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Abstract—This paper presents a LiDAR-based self-localization method for autonomous vehicles on racetracks, without relying on the global navigation satellite system (GNSS) technology. The methodology leverages a-priori knowledge of fixed geo-referenced landmarks (e.g., pylons) in the racetrack environment to achieve accurate vehicle positioning by processing LiDAR point clouds. We design a processing pipeline to extract a set of candidate detections, which are then associated to the known pylons along the racing circuit and integrated in a Bayesian tracking filter for vehicle self-localization. The proposed method is validated with the RACECAR dataset, the first open dataset for full-scale and high-speed autonomous racing of the Indy autonomous challenge. Performance results highlight an average positioning mismatch of 1.42 m with respect to GNSS real time kinematic.

Index Terms—Autonomous vehicles, Bayesian tracking, LiDAR, localization, positioning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development and commercialization of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) aim to reduce traffic accidents and improve transportation safety [1]. The paradigm shift from human drivers to autonomous control of vehicles has been empowered by technological breakthroughs that enable CAVs to accurately monitor their surrounding environment and actuate control strategies [2]. Such enhancements are not only related to urban mobility, they have also tackled autonomous racing [3], [4]. Compared to the first case, an autonomous racing scenario is characterized by extreme mobility conditions which challenge the performance of positioning, perception and control tasks. The very high speed (up to up to 274 km/h [5]) of a racing event unavoidably poses stringent requirements on the accuracy and integrity of the onboard perception systems. The Indy autonomous challenge (IAC) is the latest frontier of autonomous racing, where Dallara AV-21 vehicles from university research teams participate in different competitions [5]–[8]. Similar challenges and events animate passionate scholars and researchers since several years, with a diverse range of robot cars, varying in scale from 1:10 to full-scale [9], [10].

For safe autonomous navigation, an accurate and reliable positioning system is mandatory to guarantee the vehicle a

spatial awareness in the racetrack environment. Despite the global navigation satellite system (GNSS) technology being the primary solution for vehicle positioning thanks to its worldwide coverage, easy usability and integration in onboard systems, it is subject to signal degradation or temporary unavailability that prevent the autonomous navigation as the position estimate becomes unreliable. GNSS augmentation solutions such as satellite-based augmentation system (SBAS), ground-based augmentation system (GBAS), and real-time kinematic (RTK) guarantee an accuracy of 1 m or below [11], but still suffer from issues related to availability and integrity. For this reason, a multi-sensor fusion approach is recommended, where GNSS technology is integrated and fused with other onboard perception or communication sensor data [12]–[16].

To overcome the GNSS unavailability issue, GNSS-free techniques should be developed, aiming to be individually accurate and reliable. At the same time, they need to be seamlessly integrated with GNSS positioning. In this context, unless there is a roadside infrastructure localizing vehicles and forwarding their positions [17], vehicles can exploit the presence of static objects for self-positioning, e.g., through simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [18]–[20] or cooperative processing algorithms [21]–[25]. SLAM enables vehicles to self-localize themselves and concurrently build a map of the surrounding environment typically via cameras or LiDAR sensors [26]–[30]. Regardless of the imaging sensor adopted, SLAM methods might require large processing and memory overheads that are necessary to store and dynamically update the map [31]. Besides, the self-positioning features of SLAM might be impaired by environments that do not contain distinctive visual features. Lastly, when dealing with multiple sensors on the same vehicle, a precise calibration is crucial for high-quality and accurate map and scan matching.

LiDAR-based sensing guarantees an extremely accurate perception of the environment [32], classifying, tracking, and predicting the intention of detected objects. Its working principle is based on the steering of laser beams inside a specified field of view, which guarantees high ranging accuracy and provides an environmental map of 3D point clouds whose intensities correspond to the reflected laser energy. The ability of LiDAR sensors in detecting poles thanks to their distinctive geometric features has been shown in the recent literature on vehicular applications [33], [34]. We pursue this research track by proposing a GNSS-free LiDAR-based solution for

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autonomous vehicle positioning in a racetrack environment.

This paper presents a methodology for autonomous vehicle self-positioning on racetracks without using GNSS technology. We rely on an a-priori knowledge of environmental landmarks (pylons in this case); their detection through LiDAR sensing allows a vehicle running on track to self-positioning. Essentially, it is our goal to detect the landmarks from the point cloud, associate them with their corresponding a-priori geo-referenced information, and use such detection to let the autonomous vehicle self-locate along the racetrack. With the only requirement of performing a preliminary survey on the surrounding to identify and locate the detectable landmarks, we design and evaluate a processing pipeline that extracts the estimated locations of landmarks from the raw LiDAR point cloud. Differently from road mobility where the vehicle trajectory spans over a wide and highly-varying area, a race-track scenario is easier to be managed with prior inspections and identification of relevant landmarks (e.g., to be performed before the racing days). In other words, it is possible to accurately learn the scenario and calibrate the algorithms in advance, i.e., before online validation while racing.

The proposed methodology emerges as an assistance or replacement solution to GNSS for vehicle positioning. Relying on an additional positioning solution increases the robustness of a standalone satellite-based system, which can occasionally undergo outage conditions. In the latter case, the autonomous vehicle is likely to have incidents or enter a safe mode by decelerating and proceeding at very low speed or even stop. The validation on the RACECAR dataset (Las Vegas motor speedway) [5] allows to remarkably understand the performances in real autonomous racing conditions, i.e., providing a tangible assessment on the achieved results. The obtained results show an average accuracy of 1.42 m; despite it is not sufficient to guarantee a standalone system for autonomous navigation, it represents a highly promising direction for enriching the set of positioning systems available on the vehicle in a sensor fusion unit. Nevertheless, it stands out as a reliable backup solution when GNSS positioning is unavailable.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROCESSING PIPELINE

This section describes the modeling of the driving scenario (Sec. II-A) and presents the processing pipeline designed to extract the coordinates of landmarks from the raw LiDAR point cloud (Sec. II-B).

A. System model

Consider a moving vehicle collecting LiDAR acquisitions over time. The LiDAR scans its surroundings and collects thousands of individual distance measurements from back-scattering objects. Each distance is referred to a spatial coordinate in 3D space, having the LiDAR sensor as the origin of the reference frame itself. A scan at time t is defined as the set \mathcal{P}_t containing four-dimensional points described by their 3D coordinates in space and their reflected intensity.

The true vehicle state is described by $\mathbf{v}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 1}$, which includes the 2D position and 2D velocity. The vehicle moves

along a pre-defined environment, i.e., a racetrack, where it is possible to exploit recurrent sensing patterns and having a-priori information on the landmarks. The goal of the vehicle is to identify pylons from a set of detected landmarks estimated by processing the set \mathcal{P}_t . By applying a pipeline of algorithms, the vehicle is able to locate itself with respect to the pylons. The pylon coordinates are assumed to be known a priori (e.g., through on-field measurements), and the exact number of existing pylons is known as well. Define the true 2D coordinate of the m -th pylon as $\mathbf{x}_m \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 2}$, with $m = 1, \dots, N_p$, i.e., N_p pylons overall. The matrix containing the 2D coordinates of all pylons is denoted as $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1^T \dots \mathbf{x}_{N_p}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times 2}$.

In the following, we describe the processing pipeline of our solution that allows to sequentially refine the raw point cloud \mathcal{P}_t and identify the subset of detected pylons at every scan.

B. Processing pipeline

We here describe the sequence of algorithms applied to the raw LiDAR point cloud to detect landmarks, explaining each procedure of the processing pipeline illustrated in Fig. 1. To avoid redundant notation, the subscript t denoting the time index is not used in this section.

1) *Point cloud windowing*: As first processing operation, our aim is to reduce the dimension of the raw point cloud. Denote with \mathcal{P} the lidar point cloud of the vehicle surroundings. Considering the constrained motion direction on a racetrack and the physical installations of landmarks to be detected, a specific region of interest (ROI) can be enforced. In our case, the counterclockwise motion and the pylon positions in the outer area with respect to the track allow us to specify the ROI in which to detect the pylon landmarks in the right-hand side of the vehicle, as shown in the left inset in Fig. 1. Notice that such preliminary filtering operation can also benefit from additional information on the environment, such as the maximum distance of pylons with respect to a plausible vehicle trajectory, which allows to further refine the windowing (as in our case where the point clouds located at high distances are removed). We implement a windowing on \mathcal{P} to reduce the raw point cloud to a rectangular prism \mathcal{P}' defining such ROI. This resizing reduces the volume of the point cloud data from a horizontal field of view (HFOV) of 360 deg to a narrower area with a higher probability of pylon detection. This operation is calibrated on the dimension of the racetrack, i.e., changing the racetrack would request a redefinition of the windowing parameters.

2) *Point cloud clustering with DBSCAN algorithm*: The goal here is to identify and isolate physical objects (including pylons) by exploiting their geometrical properties. Considering the prism $\mathcal{P}' = \{\mathbf{p}_k\}_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{P}'|}$, being \mathbf{p}_k the individual 3D point belonging to the ROI, we project the points on the horizontal plane. From now on, the altitude component is neglected and the processing applies to 2D components. Using the density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) algorithm allows to cluster the detected objects by identifying sub-regions with high density of points. Specifically,

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the processing pipeline from the raw point cloud \mathcal{P} to the subset of detected pylons $\tilde{\mathcal{X}}$. The visualization of two processing stages is reported as well.

the DBSCAN algorithm enables to obtain a segmentation of the input set \mathcal{P}' into complementary subsets \mathcal{C}_i , with $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ based on the spatial distribution of its elements, i.e., performing the following mapping rule:

$$\mathcal{P}' \mapsto \mathcal{C}_{\text{DBSCAN}} = \{\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_N\}, \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{C}_i \subseteq \mathcal{P}', \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{P}' = \mathcal{C}_1 \cup \mathcal{C}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{C}_N, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_1 \cap \mathcal{C}_2 \cap \dots \cap \mathcal{C}_N = 0. \quad (4)$$

To this extent, it requires a radius parameter ϵ (here set to 40 cm) that defines the maximum distance between two points to consider them as neighbors and the minimum number of points N_{\min} required to form a dense region (here set to 1). A point is considered a core point if there are at least N_{\min} points (including itself) within its neighborhood. Points within existing regions that do not satisfy this condition are labeled as border points and cannot expand the cluster.

3) *Size-based filtering*: Here, we aim to further refine each cluster \mathcal{C}_i generated by the DBSCAN algorithm to identify the pylons. Due to their slim and tall shape, pylons are significantly different from the other objects in the environment such as guardrails and advertisement banners. The pylon-generated clusters have almost the same cardinality; this facilitates their detection with a threshold-based approach. To this purpose, we specify a lower and an upper thresholds (Γ_{\min} and Γ_{\max} , respectively) and use a size-based filter which categorically filters out each cluster \mathcal{C}_i associated to objects either excessively small or large. The survival clusters are saved in the set \mathcal{C}_{SB} obtained as:

$$\mathcal{C}_{\text{SB}} = \{\mathcal{C}_i \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{DBSCAN}} : \Gamma_{\min} \leq |\mathcal{C}_i| \leq \Gamma_{\max}\}_{i=1}^N, \quad (5)$$

being $|\mathcal{C}_i|$ the size of cluster \mathcal{C}_i . The thresholds Γ_{\min} and Γ_{\max} need be tuned depending on the size of the landmarks and the scanning frequency of the LiDAR sensor which can lead to a denser description of the surrounding space.

4) *Centroid computation*: The goal here is to describe each survived cluster in \mathcal{C}_{SB} with a unique 2D centroid. The centroid well approximates the location of the detected object (i.e., pylon), allowing for a more efficient and concise representation of a cluster. Considering the single cluster of points $\mathcal{C}_i = \{\mathbf{p}_{k,i}\}_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{C}_i|}$, being $\mathbf{p}_{k,i}$ the individual 2D point of the i -th cluster, the associated centroid is computed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_i = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}_i|} \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{C}_i|} \mathbf{p}_{k,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 1}. \quad (6)$$

Define $\mathcal{M} = \{\boldsymbol{\mu}_i\}_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}_{\text{SB}}|}$ the set of centroids at this stage of the processing pipeline. The measured distance of each centroid with respect to the LiDAR position (recall that all the points are measured in cartesian coordinates with respect to the position of the LiDAR) is denoted as $z_i = \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_i\|$.

5) *Layout-based filtering*: Since road pylons have a nearly equidistant placement (for uniform illumination reasons), we exploit this characteristic to discard the centroids that do not comply with such a regular pattern. By computing the distances between adjacent centroids, we are able to identify and discard the ones that do not conform to the geometric patterns of the landmarks given by the specific racetrack layout. Given two centroids $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_j$, with $i \neq j$, the distance $d_{i,j} = \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_j\|$ is compared to layout-dependent thresholds. Specifically, in our case, considering that the distance between two adjacent pylons is ≈ 30 m, any centroid which does not comply with such geometrical pattern is discarded.

6) *Centroid-pylon association*: As last processing stage of the pipeline, the survived centroids need to be associated to the pylons available as a-priori information about the racetrack environment. To this purpose, we logically divide the ROI into N_p subregions, each containing at most one pylon, and exploit the sequential pattern of detections to associate each centroid to the originating pylon. The desired goal is to exactly map N_p centroids to the N_p pylons in the ROI, one for each subregion. The division is based on the definition of a fixed inter-pylon distance d_p (whose value depends on the layout).

Upon association, it is possible to use the detected pylons as landmarks to perform self-positioning. Formally, this operation is done through a mapping function $\psi(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{x}_m)$ defined as:

$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{x}_m) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \boldsymbol{\mu}_i \not\mapsto \mathbf{x}_m, \\ 1 & \text{if } \boldsymbol{\mu}_i \mapsto \mathbf{x}_m, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

which specifies the absence ($\psi(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{x}_m) = 0$) or presence ($\psi(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{x}_m) = 1$) of the mapping from $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ to \mathbf{x}_m .

In case the association step leads to non-unique assignments, i.e., there are more than one centroids assigned to the same pylon \mathbf{x}_m , ambiguities arise and give rise to errors (see right inset in Fig. 1). Moreover, another type of association error is related to a wrong association due to an estimation error on the centroid coordinates. While the latter error is unavoidable, the first one needs to be resolved to have a unique centroid-pylon association. For this reason, when multiple associations occur, we only consider the most likely centroid (i.e., the one that mostly matches the geometrical pattern specified by the inter-pylon distance), discarding the others. The detected pylons through the sequential processing pipeline from the raw point cloud \mathcal{P} are stored in the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} \subseteq \mathbf{X}$, with $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{N}_p \times 2}$ and the number of detected pylons $\tilde{N}_p \leq N_p$.

C. Vehicle tracking

Upon the association of the detected centroids to the true pylons, it is possible to use each pylon as a reference point for vehicle self-positioning by relying on the corresponding ranging measurement $z_{i,t}$. Defining the vector $\mathbf{z}_t = [z_{1,t} \cdots z_{\tilde{N}_p,t}]^T$ of available ranging measurements from the LiDAR location to the detected pylons at time t , it is our goal to track the vehicle state \mathbf{v}_t over time. The estimate is indicated with $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_t$ and it is computed as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_t = \int \mathbf{v}_t p(\mathbf{v}_t | \mathbf{z}_t) d\mathbf{v}_t, \quad (8)$$

where the vehicle state posterior probability density function (pdf) $p(\mathbf{v}_t | \mathbf{z}_t)$ is computed merging the likelihood $p(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{v}_t)$ with the prior pdf $p(\mathbf{v}_t | \mathbf{v}_{t-1})$. The computation of $p(\mathbf{v}_t | \mathbf{v}_{t-1})$ relies on the nearly-constant velocity (NCV) motion model where the vehicle is approximated as a point-mass [35]. As tracking algorithm, an extended Kalman filter (EKF) is considered [36].

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we first provide a summary description of the RACECAR dataset and how we use it (Sec. III-A), and then we show the performance results obtained by the proposed LiDAR-only solution against the global positioning system (GPS)-RTK positioning (Sec. III-B).

A. Dataset description

The RACECAR dataset [5] is selected for the performance evaluation of the proposed LiDAR-only self-localization methodology. The IAC official dataset is the first open data collection for full-scale and high-speed autonomous racing.

Fig. 2. Layout of Las Vegas motor speedway with highlights on sectors and pylon positions.

Fig. 3. GDOP of LiDAR-based self-positioning using the detectable pylons in proximity along the racetrack.

Among the available scenarios in the dataset, we here consider LiDAR and GPS-RTK (for benchmarking) measurements of the MIT-PITT-RW team in Las Vegas motor speedway (LVMS) for the assessment of the proposed self-positioning methodology.

For identification purposes, consider the division of LVMS track into four sectors (curve 1, Nellis straightaway, curve 2, and the front stretch) as indicated in Fig. 2. Since pylons are located only in three sectors (see the red dots in Fig. 2), the proposed methodology can work and be assessed only over curve 2, Nellis straightaway and curve 1. Overall, 51 pylons are identified and used as detectable objects for vehicle self-positioning, with coordinates measured by satellite maps. Notice that the latter operation might have introduced biases in the pylon coordinates, still we can consider such errors as marginally affecting the achieved positioning results. For a refined evaluation, an on-field survey with GNSS-RTK technology is recommended, but this is outside the availability of public data for our research purposes.

The analyzed sub-portion of the track with associated geometric dilution of precision (GDOP) for ranging measurements from 51 pylons is reported in Fig. 3. The graph is obtained by using, for each position, the subset of detectable pylons

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Vehicle positioning results before and after synchronization compensation. (a) Vehicle position error. (b) Longitudinal error; (c) Transversal error.

according to the LiDAR sensing range. The average number of detections is 3.4 pylons per scan.

B. Results

We compare the performances of the proposed LiDAR-based methodology for self-positioning against the GPS-RTK estimate available in the dataset, which is assumed as ground truth information. As error metric, we consider the 2-D error on vehicle position, also decomposing it along the longitudinal and transversal components of the trajectory by using the heading information available in the inertial measurement unit

Fig. 5. Estimated vehicle trajectories: comparison of the proposed LiDAR-based self-positioning approach against GPS-RTK.

(IMU) data field of the dataset. The average 2-D error over the full track is of 2.81 m, with average values on each sector of 3.45 m, 3.04 m and 1.75 m for curve 1, Nellis straightaway, and curve 2, respectively. By a deeper inspection of the estimates, we observe a constant bias in the position estimate all over the LVMS. This can be noticed by the sign of the longitudinal and transversal error components and it implies that the estimates fall underneath and behind the true position of the car. We attribute this behavior to a possible delay or mismatch between LiDAR and GPS data. As a matter of fact, considering that the vehicle speed for the analyzed scenario can reach values up to 30 m/s, even small offsets of a few hundredths of a second can result in errors of 60 – 80 cm. It thus emerges the need of having perfectly synchronized devices for a fair performance comparison. The hypothesis of the existence a slight synchronization offset lead us to evaluate the performance for different values of δ_t . We found that an offset between GPS and LiDAR sensors data of $\delta_t = 120$ ms (in this interval the vehicle travels along ≈ 2.5 m) allows to re-evaluate the performance and obtain a more faithful and reliable, as well as more accurate, positioning results. The comparison of the results by applying or not the correction (indicated with dotted and solid lines, respectively) is shown in Fig. 4. After the correction, the error is reduced by 49%, reaching an average value on the whole track of 1.42 m, and an average error for each of the three areas of 1.66 m, 1.17 m, and 1.44 m, respectively.

The obtained results are highly promising and satisfactory, as they allow to obtain a faithful trajectory estimate (as shown in Fig. 5). Still, it would be possible to further enhance them by considering the exact installation positions of sensors on the car. As a matter of fact, the reference GPS-RTK information is obtained by averaging two systems with two antennas each, located at different positions. In a similar way, the used LiDAR data are a combination of three LiDAR sensors at different locations. While their mean should be in the vehicle central position (as can be appreciated in [5, Fig. 2]), a possible residual position mismatch might exist. This information is not available in the RACECAR dataset, so it is not possible to account for such possible additional source of error at present.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a LiDAR-based positioning method able to provide vehicle positioning independent of other po-

sitioning technology (e.g., GNSS). The method is suitable for racing circuits, where it is possible to perform prior surveys for the identification of landmarks and calibrate the algorithms of the processing pipeline. It works by detecting through processing and clustering techniques landmarks (e.g., pylons), whose detection allows a vehicle to self-positioning in the environment. Ranging information is used in an EKF tracker where the vehicle is approximated as a point-mass whose dynamics over time are assumed to follow an NCV model. The results on the RACECAR dataset of the IAC demonstrated the system's effectiveness in detecting pylons within the region of interest and providing a faithful trajectory estimate of the vehicle over the racing track.

While this work represents a first assessment on the potentialities of GNSS-free positioning in vehicular racing environment, it opens a variety of possibilities for additional researches. For instance, the considered set of landmarks can be extended such that a higher number of measurements can be used for positioning. Possibly, exploiting an improved geometrical factor by identifying landmarks in the inner area of the track is suggested. Alternatively, it is also recommended to exploit deep learning model to automatically extract the vehicle position from processing the full raw point cloud, i.e., without designing a dedicated processing pipeline.

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